

Student-Centered Pedagogies in the Classroom: Teachers Experiences

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Abstract. This study explored the teachers' experiences in implementing student-centered pedagogies in the classroom. Specifically, it aimed to simultaneously answer their perceptions about it as the coping mechanism for emerging challenges. To achieve the objectives of the study, I made use of phenomenology. The 10 participants of this study are from the Davao Del Norte Division. I used a semi-structured online interview using the coding technique to analyze the data. The study disclosed different themes, such as the first objective to support students' learning experiences, actively listen to students' concerns, and be an adaptable professional. Another objective was to cope with the challenges of collecting results. The themes were Continuous Professional Development, Collaboration and Support Networks, and Seeking Student Feedback. In summary, teachers in student-centered pedagogies act as facilitators, prioritize individual needs and interests, promote collaboration and critical thinking, and create inclusive learning environments. These perceptions highlight the fundamental principles of student-centered pedagogy, which include active learning, student engagement, personalized learning experiences, and the development of independent learners. Teachers also strive to create inclusive and equitable learning environments where students feel valued and respected. Ultimately, the goal was to develop independent learners who were motivated and empowered to take ownership of their education. Creating inclusive and equitable learning environments was another essential aspect of a student-centered pedagogy.

KEY WORDS

1. learner-centered 2. pedagogies 3. approaches

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1. Introduction

Implementing student-centered pedagogies in the classroom often enriches the learning experience for both students and teachers, as it shifts the focus from rote memorization to active engagement and critical thinking. Teachers who embrace student-centered approaches find themselves transitioning from traditional authority figures to facilitators of knowledge, fostering a collaborative learning environment where students take ownership of their education. Through personalized instruction, varied assessments, and fostering a culture of inquiry, teachers witness students' heightened motivation, deeper understanding of concepts, and enhanced problem-solving skills. Despite the challenges of adopting such pedagogies, teachers often express fulfillment in witnessing their students' growth and empowerment, highlighting the transformative impact of student-centered education on both academic and personal devel-

opment. It's important for instructors to understand their roles and responsibilities in the new classroom environments if novel pedagogies are to be implemented successfully. The literature on student-centered classrooms outlines the teacher's obligations in settings where student-centered pedagogies, such as various forms of constructivist and inquiry-based learning, are used. In constructivist classes, "(t)he teachers' role is to encourage and accept student autonomy and create a comfortable environment for student expression," functioning as guides for their pupils, according to Moustafa et al. (2019). One global issue related to student-centered pedagogies is the exacerbation of educational inequality. While student-centered approaches can empower students and improve learning outcomes, they may also widen the gap between students from privileged backgrounds who have access to resources and support, and those from marginalized communities who lack such advantages. Addressing this issue requires ensuring equitable access to quality education and providing adequate support for teachers to implement student-centered practices effectively across diverse socio-economic contexts. In United Kingdom, the exacerbation of educational inequality through student-centered pedagogies underscores the complex interplay between teaching methodologies and socio-economic disparities. While these pedagogical approaches aim to empower students by fostering critical thinking, collaboration, and self-directed learning, their success hinges on equitable access to resources and support Hagger (2020). However, students from marginalized communities often face systemic barriers such as inadequate funding, insufficient infrastructure, and limited access to technology, which hinder their ability to fully benefit from student-centered practices. Moreover, teachers serving in under-resourced schools may encounter challenges in implementing these approaches due to large class sizes, limited instructional time, and lack of

professional development opportunities. Thus, addressing educational inequality requires a multi-faceted approach that tackles systemic inequities while providing targeted support to educators and students in marginalized communities, Johnson (2020). In Asia, to mitigate the exacerbation of educational inequality, policymakers must prioritize equity in education policy and resource allocation, ensuring that all students have access to the necessary tools and opportunities to thrive in student-centered classrooms. This entails investing in initiatives that promote equitable distribution of funding, technology, and learning materials, as well as providing tailored support for teachers in high-needs schools. Professional development programs should focus on equipping educators with culturally responsive teaching strategies, classroom management techniques, and assessment practices that foster inclusivity and address diverse learning needs. Additionally, partnerships between schools, communities, and local stakeholders can facilitate the implementation of holistic support systems that address the social, emotional, and academic needs of students from marginalized backgrounds. By addressing the root causes of educational inequality and providing targeted interventions, societies can create more equitable learning environments where all students have the opportunity to thrive and succeed. Another global challenge is the need for comprehensive teacher training and ongoing professional development in student-centered pedagogies. Many educators may lack the necessary skills, resources, or support to implement these approaches effectively. Consequently, there's a global imperative to invest in teacher training programs that equip educators with the knowledge and tools to employ student-centered methods, fostering a culture of continuous learning and improvement within the teaching profession. Teacher training and ongoing professional development in student-centered pedagogies are crucial for enhancing

educators' ability to implement effective teaching practices. As noted by Fullan and Hargreaves (2019), investing in high-quality professional development programs is essential for ensuring that teachers have the necessary skills and support to adapt their teaching methods to meet the diverse needs of students. Without adequate training, educators may struggle to implement student-centered approaches effectively, resulting in limited student engagement and achievement (Darling-Hammond, Hyler, Gardner, 2019). Therefore, there is a global imperative to prioritize teacher training initiatives that emphasize evidence-based instructional strategies, collaborative learning techniques, and formative assessment methods (Hattie, 2022). By fostering a culture of continuous learning and improvement within the teaching profession, these programs can empower educators to create inclusive, student-centered learning environments that promote academic success and lifelong learning. Implementing student-centered pedagogies also raises issues related to cultural and contextual adaptation. What works well in one cultural or educational context may not be as effective in another. Therefore, educators and policymakers must consider the cultural nuances and socio-economic realities of different communities when designing and implementing student-centered approaches. This requires a holistic approach that incorporates local perspectives, values, and needs, while also ensuring alignment with broader educational goals and standards. Implementing student-centered pedagogies necessitates a nuanced understanding of cultural and contextual factors that influence teaching and learning practices. As highlighted by Anderson (2020), learning is inherently socio-cultural, shaped by the social and cultural contexts in which it occurs. Therefore, educators and policymakers must consider the unique cultural nuances and socio-economic realities of diverse communities when designing and implementing student-centered approaches (Gay,

2019). Meanwhile, in the Philippines the Department of Education (DepEd) is eyeing more improvements in the delivery of education for the upcoming school year. In order to fulfill their new roles, teachers must shift their focus in the classroom from lecturing to assessing. Inquiry-based teachers become assessors because "it can help in diagnosing students' prior knowledge, gauging students' understanding throughout the learning experience and guiding instruction, and measuring their understanding and knowledge at the completion of the learning experience" (Bao, 2019). In other words, the facilitator maintains the focus on learning, guides the process, meters the challenge, and provides appropriate feedback to each student and the whole group" (Dodge et al. 2019). This change in focus represents a dramatic shift from past practice. Some of the difficulties teachers have when using student-centered pedagogies are described in the literature. The lack of flexibility in the classroom worries about students' performance on external exams (Dwivedi 2021), resistance to change from traditional methods (Garcia, 2020), peer pressure from other teachers, and concerns about time to cover the curriculum have all been identified as barriers to becoming student-centered. This literature focuses on the justifications given by instructors for their opposition. Locally, the Division of Davao Del Norte has implemented the 21st Teaching Pedagogies in response to the schools conducted profiling of the learning facilitators at home to know if they can facilitate instruction with the modular approach to learning. With all these changes, teachers are forced to adapt and upskill in order to continually monitor the status of the learners. Information technology skills become a significant part of learning during the new normal in order to facilitate the instruction better, give feedback and reach the struggling learners remotely. As educators switched from providing instruction in person in the classroom to virtually from a distance, the enormous and sudden

move to remote learning gained widespread media coverage. Although there has undoubtedly been a lot of turbulence in the past few months, teachers' feeling of job security is probably considerably greater than that of many other working professionals. Indeed, there is really a need to facilitate the students learning with the use of student-centered pedagogies. This literature focuses on the reasons teachers provide for resisting implementation, most of which focus on students rather than what the teachers believe about themselves as they attempt to be student-

centered. While some reports of teacher stress are connected to reform-related curricula that include mandates for student-centered instruction, little literature addresses the impact on teachers as they implement student-centered pedagogy (Lewis , 2019), the focus of the current study. As the teacher identity literature reviewed below indicates, understanding the impacts of this dramatic environmental change on teachers' identity is critical for understanding and affecting teachers' instructional decision-making.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The study aimed to explore teachers' experiences in implementing student-centered pedagogies. The findings of this study were potentially beneficial for administrators, as the data gathered served as research-based information that could be utilized to motivate and provide technical assistance to teachers in implementing student-centered learning, including its challenges and opportunities. Additionally, the study offered potential benefits for teachers, enabling them to prepare for and adapt to changes in school culture, particularly during the height of a global pandemic. Furthermore, the results generated comprehensive data that could inform future research with similar or relevant scope.

- 1.2. Research Questions*—The primary research questions of this study were the following:
- (1) What are the experiences of teachers in implementing student-centered pedagogies in the classroom?
 - (2) How teachers cope with the challenges in implementing a student-centered approach in the classroom?
 - (3) What educational management insights are gained from the study?

1.3. Definition of Terms—The following terms were defined for use in this study: Student-centered pedagogy was described as a teaching method that focuses on creating connections between students' interests and what

they learn in school. The goal is to make the educational process more meaningful to students. Teacher Experiences were described as the various interactions, activities, challenges, and milestones educators encounter throughout their careers.

1.4. Significant of the Study—This study was significant for various stakeholders: DepEd Officials could utilize the findings as an empirical basis for developing new programs aimed at enhancing student-centered classrooms. School Administrators could leverage the gathered data as research-based information to motivate and provide technical support to teachers, particu-

larly in innovating methodologies, including those related to information communication technology, amidst the challenges and opportunities faced. Teachers could benefit from the study by improving the teaching-learning process in distance learning setups, thereby enhancing academic proficiency through the integration of new student-centered classroom ap-

proaches. Stakeholders, including the community, could also benefit from the study's findings as they contribute to the adoption of new normal innovations within the institution, potentially aiding in the improvement of the school's organizational changes. Additionally, Future

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This study was anchored on Kolb and Fry (1975), looked at the constituent parts of reflection and, from these, created a learning cycle framework. Kolb identified four parts of the learning cycle. To make Kolb's model more understandable, Pedler, Burgoyne, and Boydell (2021) simplified the terminology. Kolb highlights an important point. Individuals tend to have a preference for carrying out one part of the learning cycle over the others. For example, theorizing in the 'abstract conceptualization' or the 'so what' in Pedler's model. In many cases this is not problematic, so long as a level of skill is maintained in the other areas. However, if an individual develops a very strong preference for one part of the cycle, then they may neglect and become deskilled in the other areas. This can cause the subsequent learning to become skewed and unbalanced. Therefore, maintaining a level of competence in all parts of the learning cycle is essential to ensure comprehensive learning. John Dewey was thought to be the founder of reflection as it relates to personal learning. Dewey highlighted that reflection in a learning context is not just a passive recall of an event. Reflection is a deliberate and active process. It is about thinking about learning. In Dewey's words, it is an "active, persistent and careful consideration of any belief or supposed form of knowledge in the light of the grounds that support it, and further conclusions to which it leads" (Dewey, 1933). Dewey believed that reflection could be useful for making sense of situations or events that we found puzzling or hard to explain. He suggested that reflection for learning should include recalling the event

Researchers could utilize the results generated as comprehensive data for conducting future research with similar or relevant scope, providing additional empirical evidence for an efficient learning process.

and then posing questions to explore why things turned out the way they did and what possible actions could have given a different outcome. Since Dewey's initial work, a variety of models have been proposed to capture the components of reflection within learning. Student-centered pedagogy is defined as "an instructional approach in which students influence the content, activities, materials, and pace of learning" (Collins O'Brien, 2003). Student-centered pedagogy is thus dialogical and reciprocal between the teacher and students and among students. Dewey rejected the widely accepted theory at the time that children were "passive recipients of knowledge (Janse, 2019). This commonly accepted theory of the period left children in "desks that were in rows in the classroom and students would not leave their chair all day" (Janse, 2019). However, Dewey proposed a different application within schools which "recommends an interdisciplinary curriculum, or a curriculum that focuses on connecting multiple subjects where students can walk freely in and out of classrooms. In this way, they pursue their interests and build their method for acquiring and applying specific knowledge" (Janse, 2019). This method works by students taking the initiative to recognize their interests and applying their ever-changing skill sets and knowledge to tasks at hand. At the same time, the teacher provides direction and the space for the students to learn, grow, and ultimately thrive. By setting the environment for the students to learn and stepping back, the teacher facilitates those students to think critically and develop problem-solving skills by adapting to the obstacles they face on

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

their assignments and tasks. The conceptual framework of the study is presented in Figure 1. Based on the figure, there are three interconnected working themes. These working themes are the experiences of teaching personnel in the organizational changes encountered in the new

everyday innovations, challenges encountered by the teaching personnel in the organizational changes in their private institution, and educational management insights gained by the teaching personnel in the organizational changes in their private institutions.

2. Methodology

This chapter introduced the methods used in conducting the study and gathering data. It also included the research design, philosophical assumptions, research participants and sampling, data collection, research instrument, the trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. The three most common qualitative methods were participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method was particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation was appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth interviews (IDI) were optimal for collecting data on individuals' personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when sensitive topics were being explored. Focus groups were effective in eliciting data on the cultural norms of a group and in generating broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. Patton (2019) defined phenomenology as inquiry that asked the question, "What is the structure and essence of the experience of this phenomenon for these people?" The goal of this research

worked well with this definition in trying to understand the experiences of the school heads in the new normal as they tried to compare its implementation then and now. Giorgi (2019) cautioned researchers to be prepared for an investigation that was greater in both depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested information be viewed as only the tip of the iceberg.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption is a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret data in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used to reach conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. Good research begins with the selection of the topic, problem, or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Decent study task jumps with the range of the topic, problem, or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Stanage (2019) traced the 'paradigm' back to its Greek (paradeigma) and Latin origins (paradigm) meaning pattern, model, or example. A paradigm is the patterning of the thinking of a person; it is a principal example among examples of an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions are taken. Differently stated, a paradigm is an act of submitting to a view (Stanage, 2019). This view is supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2020), who define a research paradigm as a “basic set of beliefs that guide action,” dealing with first principles, ‘ultimates,’ or the researcher’s worldview or philosophy. Ontology. This part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012), reality was subjective and multiple, as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. Reality is constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, realities on the implementation of the curriculum in the past and the present were discussed by the participants and tries to look into their ways in coping with the implementation in the new normal. In this study, I relied on voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes, themes that reflected their words and provided evidences of different perspectives. The answers of the participants to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct for the commonality and discreteness of responses. I made sure that the responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure reliability of result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precludes from making personal bias as the study progress. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible as during the study in order obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln (1985) as cited by Creswell (2013) state that on epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen distance himself or herself from the participants. He suggests that being a researcher he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an “insider.” Based on Davidson (2020) and Jones (2021) I would identify phenomenology with the use of thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers “hold explicit belief”. I assured to establish a close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that would shed light to the knowledge behind the inquiry, particularly on the experiences and the coping strategies of the teachers in implementing the program in the new normal. Axiology refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2019) avers that the role of values in a study is significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes

his own interpretation in conjunction with an interpretation of participants. I uphold the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understands the personal and the value-laden nature of information gathered from the study. I therefore preserve the merit of the participant's answers and carefully interpreted the answers in the light of the participant's personal interpre-

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—The methodology was different from the method. The methodology is a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study, the experiences of the teachers were explored, particularly among the ten (10) teachers from New Corella National High School. The researcher's drive to know the deeper meaning of their experiences became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means which Kalof and Dietz (2020), as cited from Gerodias (2019), considered helpful in looking for "meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena." By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the stories of the floating teachers in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols and meaning of the experiences were presented. Phenomenological research is based on two

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—This study employed a qualitative approach to research specifically a phenomenological research design. According to Creswell, (2019), phenomenology was an approach to qualitative research that focused on the commonality of lived experiences within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach is to arrive at a description of the nature of the particular

tation. Rhetoric. This philosophical assumption stressed that the researcher may write in a literary, informal style using the personal voice and uses qualitative terms and limited definition. In the context of the study, the researcher used the first person in the elucidation of the experiences of the teachers as they adopt to the new mode of learning implementation amidst the pandemic.

premises. The first was that experience is a valid, rich and rewarding source of knowledge. According to Becker (2020), as cited in Morrissey Higgs, (2020), that experience is a source of knowledge and shapes one's behavior. From the definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not as an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge, and that we can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2020). By doing phenomenology which concerns with that "what" and the "how" (Moustakas, 2020), the researcher projected that the subjective experiences, challenges and coping mechanisms of the physical education teachers were explored and insights were drawn as basis for the possible future researches and policy analysis in relation to this research.

phenomenon. Typically, interviews were conducted with a group of individuals who have first-hand knowledge of an event, situation or experience. Other forms of data such as documents, observations and art were also used. The data were read and reread and was culled for phrases and themes that was grouped into clusters of meanings. Through this process, the researcher was able to construct the universal

meaning of the event, situation or experience and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. Moreover, Maxwell (2019) also added that with the roots in philosophy, psychology and education, phenomenology attempt to extract the purest, untainted data and in some interpretations of the approach, bracketing were used by the researcher to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or herself from the process. One method of bracketing is taking of notes. According to Corbetta (2020), the phenomenological research design is a qualitative type of research for which interviews provide an in-depth method that can grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and help grasp the subjects' perspective. Creswell, (2019) also claimed that interviews are primarily done in qualitative research and occur when researchers ask one or more participants general, open-ended questions and record their answers. Often audio tapes were utilized to allow more consistent transcription. Interviews are also useful to follow up with individual respondents after questionnaires, such as to further investigate their responses. In qualitative research, interviews were used to pursue the meanings of central themes in the world of their subjects. The main task in doing interviews is to understand the meaning of what the interviewees say (McNamara, 2019). Withal, based on the statements of Quad (2020), the researcher transcribed and typed the data into a computer file in order to analyze it after interviewing. Interviews exceptionally be helpful in uncovering the story behind a participant's experiences and pursuing in-depth information about a topic. The researcher collected data, typically via extended interviews, from individuals who have experienced the phenomenon under investigation. Next, the data analysis involved triangulation

that extracted significant statements from the transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each statement fell under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied up together to make a general description of the experience both the textural description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it was experienced. The researcher incorporated his or her personal meaning of the experiences here. Finally, the report was written such that readers understand better the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed out. The researcher required a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects that were selected into the study were individuals who have actually experienced the phenomenon. The researcher needed to bracket his or her own experiences and observations, which was difficult to do. The researcher also needed to decide how and when his or her personal observations would be incorporated into the study. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches were based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity and emphasized the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such they were powerful tools for understanding subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the cluster of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Since the focus of this study was to explore the teaching personnel's perceptions and feelings towards the school environment and their perspectives on the new normal innovations, the researcher intended to employ phenomenological methods of qualitative research.

2.4. *Research Participants*—The participants of this study were from New Corella Na-

tional High School, Davao Del Norte Division. The participants were chosen based on the fol-

lowing criteria: (1) they must have been in service for at least 2 years. The researcher utilized the purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2019). It is also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic (Marshall, 1996). The researcher was responsible for uncovering, transferring, and exploiting knowledge to benefit educational institutions. To do so, the researcher took up the following roles in the course of the study: Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research. I conducted interviews with the participants and guided them through the process. The researcher interpreted ideas and responses based on existing literature and related studies, and not on the researcher's own knowledge, thoughts, and feelings to avoid the intrusion of bias. Expert in Qualitative Methods. I implemented the qualitative method correctly. To do so, I assessed myself and sought help from the research adviser and other research professionals. This helped exhibit competence in explaining the study without biasing the participants, conducting interviews properly according to the design, making appropriate field observations, selecting appropriate artifacts, images, and journal portions, and employing Environmental Triangulation and Thematic Content Analysis precisely.

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—Ethical considerations were significant in the design of this research study. The researcher needed to consider several ethical issues regarding the research participants in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations were specified as one of the most important parts of the research. The researcher needed to adhere to promoting the aims of the research, imparting authentic knowledge and truth, and preventing error. Social Value. Research was very essential to society. In this

Collector and Keeper of Data. I ensured different ways of making a record of what was said and done during the interviews and Focus Group Discussions, such as taking handwritten notes or audio and/or video recording. The recordings were transcribed verbatim before data analysis began. Records made by the researcher were properly secured as they contained sensitive information and were relevant to the research. While the data were being collected, the primary responsibility of the researcher was to safeguard participants and their data. Mechanisms for such safeguarding were clearly articulated to participants and approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research began. Analyst of Data. I saw the phenomenon or problem from the participants' perspective by interpreting data, transcribing and checking, reading between the lines, coding, and theming. I ensured that the findings were true to the participants and that their voices were heard. Organizer and Presenter of Data. I presented the problem and the related literature and studies that supported it. The findings of the study were presented by the research question, stating the results for each one using themes to show how the research questions were answered in the study. Moreover, the researcher gave future directions and implications of the study for improving educational policy and practices.

study, the social value was focused on the experiences of teachers. This study was specifically conducted among elementary teachers. This study also served as a basis for higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions from which classroom teachers could benefit. Thus, the social problem that pushed the interest of the researcher was the challenges faced by the teachers in the use of interactive media instruction in the classroom as a way to ameliorate teaching competence. Informed Consent.

In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of Participation, as cited by McLeod (2009), was adhered to. The invitation to the participants ensured that their participation in the research was completely voluntary in nature and based on the understanding of adequate information. The recruitment and selection of participants were lodged in the appendices of this study. Gaining the trust and support of research participants was critical to informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Walker, 2007, as cited by Pillerin, 2019). All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a signed personal acknowledgment, consent, and an indication of a willingness to participate in the study release. The purpose of the informed consent letter was to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the intent of the study, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and anticipate the information that the informants were expected to provide. All participants were required to sign and return the letter of consent to the researcher before participating in the research.

Vulnerability of Research Participants. The participants of this study were capable of answering the research instrument for they are all professional teachers in public elementary schools. Thus, the researcher assured them that as the researcher, he or she can easily be reached through the contact number and address in case there are some clarifications or questions with regard to the study. **Risks, Benefits, and Safety.** The recruitment of the respondents was free of coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the chair of the panel or panel members in case they had queries related to the study. Furthermore, in the event that respondents would experience potential discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelling to participate in any manner. Further, the researcher ensured that the respondents were safe during the survey and interview. Thus, the distribution of the questionnaire was conducted in a safe venue and administered at their convenient time. The dominant concern of this study is the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality and the minimization of risk. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent to this was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the data cannot be traced back to their real sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure the anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed output that was carried out from this study was kept in anonymity. Furthermore, all the issues were given consideration so that there would be no conflict of interest between the researcher and the respondents. Any type of misleading information, as well as representation of primary data findings in a biased way, must be avoided. **Justice.** The respondents were informed of the researcher's role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were briefed that they had to be fully honest in answering the survey questions and that any type of communication-related to the research should be done with honesty. Similarly, they were informed that they were the ones to benefit first from the study's results. **Transparency.** The results of the study were accessed by the respondents and heads of the participating schools because the information is available and would be placed on CDs or other storage devices, which can be requested from the researcher. In addition, by learning about the results of the study, classroom teachers were aware of the signifi-

cance of the study and its contribution to their well-being. Further, each of the participants was advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process and that they could be requested and allowed to verify their individual transcript after the interview was carried out. This provided the participants with the opportunity to amend or remove any information which they felt might identify them. The researcher reserved the right to employ the use of pseudonyms and change names and/or non-significant dates in the interest of protecting the identity of the participant in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that he or she possesses the needed qualifications to conduct the study. The researcher should have completed the academic requirements and passed the comprehensive examination prior to thesis writing, which was the last requirement to obtain the master's degree, and the researcher should be qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study would reach its completion. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher strived that the study can be completed successfully in the specified time and that he or she is equipped

with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee helped in the enhancement of the paper by giving the needed suggestions and recommendations for the improvement of the study. Also, the researcher ensured that he or she had enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, this study was hoped to be completed in the target time. Community Involvement. The researcher showed respect for the local traditions, culture, and views of the respondents in this study. Moreover, this study did not involve any use of deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically in the recruitment of the participants or methods of data collection. Furthermore, the researcher necessarily expressed great pleasure in the wholehearted participation of the interviewees in the conduct of the study. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher. The researcher respected other works by properly citing the author and rewrite what someone else has said his or her own way. The researcher also used quotes to indicate that the text has been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher assured that honesty was present in working on the manuscript and no intentional misrepresentation and making up of data or results was included, or purposefully put forward conclusions that are not accurate.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—In this study, I played various roles to attain the success of the study. First, I asked for permission to conduct the study which started from the Schools Division Superintendent and then to the participants of my study. As a researcher, if consented, I have recorded the actual interview to achieve the needs of this type of research. The interview's goal was to gain a deeper understanding of the experiences of the learners in the new normal way of teaching and learning. The interview would also include how the Department of Education should improve its programs. After

the needed data has been gathered, everything has been transcribed and analyzed by the researcher. However, human instruments were more important to be studied in case the quality of this research has to deal with biases and assumptions in dealing with the persons involved in the research (Greenbank, 2003) To address the validity issues of this design specifically on the method, I would ask for help from the experts. My interview guide question tool shall be checked and validated by the experts. The sampling used for the selection of my participants was under the suggestions of the expert panels.

2.7. *Data Collection*—The following was the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Data was collected to reproduce real-life communication scenarios in which the participants made oral or written contributions useful for research purposes and their learning process. Establishing rapport with the participants was an important step that allowed them to provide good data. To collect information, I developed protocols or written forms for recording data, such as interviews or observation. Additionally, I anticipated issues that may hinder or contribute to lost information. In this study, I employed the following data-gathering steps. I asked the Schools Division Superintendent for permission to conduct the study on January 25, 2024. I secured the superintendent's permission. I sent the superintendent a letter explaining the study's objectives and the participants' identification, with an attached copy of Chapters 1 and 2 and the research instrument. I only started after I received the Superintendent's approval. I asked for permission from the school heads. After securing approval from the SDS, I sent letters to the principals or school heads of the identified schools explaining the study to be conducted in their schools. I obtained consent from the participants and considered the participants' consent as informants of the study a priority; thus, I ensured permission from them and their parents/-

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gathered data. The researcher analyzed the answers of the participants from the conducted interviews using Creswell's Model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2019), themes in qualitative research are similar codes aggregated together to form a major idea in the database. Familiarization with the data was common to all forms of qualitative analysis; the researcher immersed her-

guardians. The participants were adequately oriented about the whole study process and their part as participants. I conducted the interview. I used the interview questionnaire to conduct an in-depth interview. I took participants' profiles, took notes, and recorded conversations using a sound recorder for easy transcription. Likewise, I carefully listened and actively responded during the interviews. I was transcribing the interviewees' responses. The researcher would then precisely transcribe them by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. Since the participants used their vernacular language, the researcher translated it into English. Data Coding and thematizing. Categorizing and coding the data would come after the transcription process. Themes were extracted, and participants' data were contrasted and compared. The researcher would then conduct a second round of interviews (FGD) to confirm data requiring more justification and participant feedback. The newly acquired material was carefully analyzed and added to the existing body of knowledge. Then, in order to identify patterns and trends, data were contrasted and compared between the individuals. To address the validity issues of this design, specifically the method, I asked for help from the experts. The experts checked and validated my interview guide question tool. I followed the expert panels' suggestions for the sampling of my participants.

self in and became intimately familiar with the data by reading and re-reading it and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding, a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis, involved generating pithy labels for important features of the data relevant to the broad research question guiding the analysis. Coding was not simply a method of data reduction; it was also an analytic process, so codes captured both a semantic and conceptual reading of the data. The researcher coded every

data item and ended this phase by collating all the codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes involved finding coherent and meaningful patterns in the data relevant to the research question. The researcher ended this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme. Reviewing themes required the researcher to reflect on whether the themes told a convincing and compelling story about the data, and to begin defining the nature of each individual theme and the relationship between the themes. For these tasks, Thematic Content Analysis was employed by the researcher. Thematic Content Analysis was a descriptive presentation of qualitative data in which a detailed analysis of each theme was made by identifying the ‘essence’ of each theme and constructing a concise, punchy, and informative name for each theme (Andersen, 2019). In addition, to enhance validity and create a more in-depth picture of the phenomenon, Environmental Triangulation was also employed by the researcher. It was a technique used to analyze the results of the same study using different methods of data

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—The analytical framework for this study was flexible enough to allow the researcher to either gather all of the data and then analyze it or evaluate it while it was being collected. The data collected was then sifted, charted, and categorized in line with key topics and themes during the analysis stage. This process involved familiarization, coding, developing a thematic framework, indexing, charting, mapping, and interpretation (Ritchie Spencer, 2019). The first step involves thoroughly reading and re-reading all the transcribed interviews. This step was crucial as it allowed the researchers to immerse themselves in the data, ensuring they fully understood the content and context of the participant’s responses. By repeatedly engaging with the transcriptions, the researcher began to identify recurring pat-

terns, themes, and nuances that might not be immediately apparent. This process helps build a comprehensive foundation for further analysis. In the second step, I extracted significant statements from the transcribed interviews. These were specific phrases or sentences that directly pertain to the investigated phenomenon. The goal was to isolate the most relevant and impactful parts of the data that would contribute to a deeper understanding of the subject. By focusing on these key statements, I distilled the essence of the participants’ experiences and insights. The third step involves giving meaning to the extracted significant statements. During this process, I categorized pertinent quotes into broader themes. This involves interpreting the statements to understand the underlying meanings and implications. By organizing the data

collection. The key was identifying which environmental factors, if any, might influence the information received during the study. These environmental factors were changed to see if the findings remained the same across different settings (David, 2019). This type of triangulation used different settings, locations, and other factors such as time, day, and season in which the study took place. The idea was to determine which of these factors influenced the information received, and then change these factors to see if the findings remained the same. If the findings remained unaltered under varying environmental factors, then validity could be established (Naeem Saira, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirements mentioned necessitated the use of environmental triangulation to best suit the research environment. Writing-up involved weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data, contextualizing it in relation to existing literature.

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into themes, I began to see how different aspects of the participants' experiences relate to each other and the overall phenomenon being studied. In the fourth step, I repeated steps 1 to 3 for each interview. This iterative process ensures that all interviews are analyzed in the same thorough manner. By treating each interview individually and then comparing the themes across inter-

views, the researcher identified commonalities and differences in the participants' experiences. This step was essential for building a robust and comprehensive analysis. After completing the initial analysis of all interviews, I compiled an exhaustive description of everything generated in the previous steps.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—Trustworthiness was all about establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability. In qualitative studies, trustworthiness is very important because the results and findings of the research study depend on the process of how it was conducted by the researcher. The trustworthiness of a research study was important for evaluating its worth. Due to the nature of qualitative studies, honesty in all the data and details was required. Trustworthiness made the researcher's study worthy to read, share, and be proud of. The concepts of validity and reliability were relatively foreign to the field of qualitative research. Instead of focusing on reliability and validity, qualitative researchers substituted data trustworthiness. Trustworthiness consists of the following components: credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability (Harts, 2016). Credibility contributed to a belief in the trustworthiness of data by observing the attributes of prolonged engagement. To address the issue of credibility, as many research participants as possible were interviewed until the point of saturation. Transferability was concerned with the extent to which the findings of one study could be applied to other situations. In positivist work, the concern often lies in demonstrating that the results of the work

at hand could be applied to a wider population since the findings of a qualitative project were specific to a small number of particular environments and individuals. It was impossible to demonstrate that the findings and conclusions applied to other situations and populations. Therefore, to ensure transferability, I acknowledged that it was my responsibility as a researcher to provide sufficient contextual information about the fieldwork sites to enable the reader to make such a transfer. Confirmability associated objectivity in science with the use of instruments that were not dependent on human skill and perception. It was, however, difficult to ensure real objectivity since even tests and questionnaires were designed by humans, making the intrusion of the researcher's biases inevitable. Here, steps had to be taken to help ensure, as far as possible, that the work's findings were the result of the experiences and ideas of the participants, rather than the characteristics and preferences of the researcher. Dependability involved participants evaluating the findings, interpretation, and recommendations of the study to ensure all were supported by the data received from participants of the study. Confirmability was the degree to which the findings of the research study could be confirmed by other researchers.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presented the results generated from analyzing the interview data. It presented themes that emerged from the analysis. Along with the themes were comprehensive discussions that answered the study's objectives. Before I began my discussion, I established the symbols I used

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

to present the quotations based on the responses of the participants of the study. In reference to the transcriptions of the conducted interviews, I used T01-T10 as codes to refer to the participants of the research.

3.1. Experiences of Teachers in Implementing Student-Centered Pedagogies in the Classroom—The first objective of the study was to uncover Teachers' experiences of Implementing Student-Centered Pedagogies in the Classroom. The questions gathered substantial ac-

3.1.1. Support Student Learning Experiences—The first theme was the experiences of teachers in implementing Student-Centered Pedagogies in the classroom. Supporting student learning experiences is the theme that comes out based on the answers of the teachers, of which it was emphasized that it involves creating an environment that fosters growth, engagement, and success for every student. One key aspect of supporting student learning experiences was Individualized Instruction. Recognizing that each student has unique learning needs, teachers in student-centered classrooms provide individualized instruction. They assess students' strengths, weaknesses, and interests, and tailor their teaching strategies accordingly. This may involve differentiated instruction, personalized learning plans, or flexibility in assignments and assessments. As the descriptions of important learning experiences quoted by students demonstrate, students need opportunities for their increased active involvement and responsibility in the study process together with challenges to connect theory and practice. Special care has to be given to building quality mutual relations and to organizing learning circumstances that facilitate confrontation of various opinions and participative learning. As Nightingale and O'Neil (2019) put it, when we start thinking of students

tual experiences from teachers. In a student-centered pedagogy classroom, teachers are perceived as collaborators rather than authoritative figures. This approach emphasizes the importance of teamwork and cooperation among students, fostering a sense of community within the classroom environment.

as active participants in the learning process, sharing their experience with a teacher, or as partners in the learning process, we will more easily keep focused on creating circumstances that lead to quality learning. Within the context of ensuring quality university studies and the vision of the university that strives not only for »excellence in research but also for »excellence in teaching«, the role of students as active co-designers of the studies has become indispensable. Finally, it is important for all university teachers to endeavor for quality through their reflection on their own work, looking for feedback information from students, providing optimal conditions for their own work, and creating a university culture where students are increasingly co-designers of the study process. We are convinced that habilitation criteria, which would consider a more balanced ratio between pedagogic and research work, may become a lever for higher-quality university studies. After all, it is our professional ethics that bind all teachers to strive for quality. Based on the Interview, by focusing on individualized instruction, scaffolding learning, providing feedback, promoting active learning, offering emotional and social support, and integrating technology effectively, teachers can create a supportive and engaging learning environment that empowers students to reach their full potential.

3.1.2. Active Listener to Students Concerns—To be effective in learning environments, learning must be addressed in all its dimensions, one of which encompasses the affective properties, including emotions, that individuals experience while learning. Among all active learning strategies, these are known as affective strategies. When learners exhibit positive affective behaviors while listening, active listening is realized in a more careful and motivated way. Researchers have shown that individuals who are motivated and eager to listen are more active while listening, whereas individuals who feel pressured by having to listen or who are shy became passive—in other words, less successful learners (Karadüz, 2019). Students interviewed stated that when they listen willingly, they enjoy learning, yet when they feel pressured and listen in fear, they cannot learn effectively or permanently. According to data gathered from the interviews in the present study, students demonstrated affective behaviors such as attending class on time, being motivated, being calm, enjoying the lesson, and being bored. Some students explained how they use affective listening strategies. A listening culture in which students are made passive has persisted for years in primary education. As part of this culture, a preference for students who listen to the teacher quietly, sit still, and do not make noise in learning environments has partially rendered students unable to develop linguistic skills such as listening and to self-actualize. Yet, the process of listening is a multidimensional one in which individuals participate with nonverbal and verbal language, thoughts, and emotions. As they do in their social lives, learners should use linguistic skills in formal learning environments and be able to actualize their linguistic skills without feeling pressured. The pressures of failing and of being unable to express ideas well can stifle their natural behaviors and promote their developing into individuals deprived of basic skills. Karadüz (2019) has found that students do not use listening strategies that are too multifarious. Using limited stimulation in learning environments, being rendered passive in traditional education systems, and being unable to develop sufficient strategies can cause them to become individuals who only take notes, listen to the instructor quietly, are shy about objecting, and cannot develop alternative ideas (Karadüz, 2019). Other than the verbal channel, by which students can express themselves in multiple learning activities, listening environments should also allow other senses to be used as well. Though most classroom communication revolves around instructor's speeches, the four sensory channels other than listening—namely, sight, touch, taste, and smell—can facilitate or hinder learning in normal classrooms. As such, new forms of stimulation can be provided by shifting sensory channels, though realizing such changes requires students to be primed for those sensory experiences. If done well, then the approach can refocus students' attention back to the instructor's presentation (Kenneth, 2019). To obtain correct and complete information in listening environments, listeners need to adopt an attitude of listening in a natural, comfortable way. According to Özbay (2019), instructors can best succeed in communicative listening training by offering opportunities that make it possible for students to learn via experience. Since students listen in ways that are more directed toward succeeding on examinations, they adopt a pragmatic attitude while taking notes in classes. Instead of seeing learning as a natural need, they prefer listening for information that they suspect will be useful on examinations. However, the popularity of such a strategy implies that classes do not accommodate listening processes directed toward communication, but a culture in which selective listening predominates. Students cannot listen to instructors in such environments, because they are distracted when they are uninterested. However, to be

able to communicate, students need to develop their skills of extraordinary view and critical listening (Stone, 2019). In any listening environment, many strategies are available such as setting objectives, preparing oneself mentally, guessing, using key concepts, and taking notes that determine the type, method, and technique

3.1.3. Adaptable Professional—Adaptable Professional, this is the third theme. People's lives are characterized by change, novelty, and uncertainty as they develop physically, cognitively, and emotionally across the lifespan (Martin, Nejad, Colmar, Liem, 2022). This constant flux can involve major life events such as starting school, getting married, or having children (Martin et al., 2022). It can also involve more "everyday" events such as illness, a change in job role, or a car breaking down (Ployhart Bliese, 2020). The ability to effectively react and respond in constructive ways to these situations is known as adaptability. More precisely, Liem (2022) define adaptability as an individual's capacity to "constructively regulate psycho-behavioral functions in response to new, changing, and/or uncertain circumstances, conditions and situations" (p. 66). Importantly, Martin et al.'s (2022) model of adaptability is a tripartite one involving cognitive, behavioral and emotional adaptability, and refers to modifying one's thinking, behavior, or emotions (respectively) to deal with changing, new, or uncertain situations. In conceptualizing adaptability, Martin and colleagues (2023) refer to the lifespan theory of control (Wrosch, Schulz, 2020). This theory proposes that lifespan development is impacted by an individual's capacity to play an active and effective role in adapting to the environmental opportunities and constraints (Heckhausen et al., 2020). Control also plays a key factor in this development and the concept of compensatory control is especially relevant to adaptability. Compensatory control refers to adjusting one's actions or thoughts

of listening (Worthington 2021) and whether it is effective. According to data obtained from this study, academically successful university students used different cognitive, affective, and psychomotor-based strategies to achieve active listening.

in order to respond to circumstances or events in an effective manner (Tomasik, Silbereisen, Heckhausen, 2020). However, there are some key differences between the lifespan theory of control and the tripartite model of adaptability (Martin et al., 2022). In particular, the lifespan theory of control largely focuses on goal disengagement (such as abandoning effort or striving towards a new goal), whereas adaptability is relevant to situations where individuals cannot disengage and must adapt to meet the demands of the task (Martin et al., 2022). In addition, whereas compensatory control focuses only on cognitive and behavioral adjustment, the tripartite model of adaptability also considers emotional adjustment (Lorenzo 2020). Notwithstanding these two differences, the lifespan theory of control provides an important theoretical basis for understanding the adaptability construct and how it functions. At this point, it is important to note that although related, adaptability is different from cognate processes such as coping and resilience. Coping refers to cognitive and behavioral efforts to manage difficult or challenging demands (Lazarus Folkman, 2019) and resilience involves successful adaptation in the face of adversity (Howard Johnson, 2020). Thus, whereas coping and resilience involve responses to adversity, adaptability concerns responses to change, novelty, and uncertainty that may be positive or negative in nature (Hagaven et al., 2019). Indeed, Johnson et al. (2019) examined adaptability among students alongside academic buoyancy, which has been called "everyday resilience" and refers to students' ability to effectively navi-

Fig. 3. Experiences of teachers on implementing Student-Centered Pedagogies in the classroom

gate typical academic setbacks and challenges (e.g., a poor grade, competing deadlines; Morse, 2020). The results showed that adaptability explained unique variance in educational and personal well-being outcomes beyond the effects of academic buoyancy. It is also worth mentioning that in addition to being defined as an outcome (as described above), resilience can also be defined as a profile involving risk and protective

factors (Mansfield et al., 2021). Figure 3 shows the emerging themes from teachers' experiences in implementing student-centered pedagogies in the classroom. The first theme that emerged was Supporting student learning experiences; based on the interview, when students are supported well, they will also do well in class. They are motivated to learn and interact with the class and their teachers.

3.2. *Coping mechanism of teachers in the challenges encountered in the implementation of student-centered pedagogies in the class-*

room—Another objective of the study is to explore the different coping mechanisms that teachers may experience.

3.2.1. *Continuous Professional Development*—The argument for the indisputable role and heavy burden put on the shoulders of teachers is well manifested in the saying that no nation can be great or rise above the quality of its educational system, and no educational system can rise above the quality of its teachers. Simply put, nourishing teacher quality is the key to properly erecting the cornerstones of the educa-

tional system and society at large (Borg, 2018, Pishghadam et al., 2019). Two qualities which may show teachers the right way in this career journey is their inclination toward education-based research practice and attending to their Continuing Professional Development (CPD) needs. Continuous Professional Development (CPD) is essential for maintaining and enhancing teacher quality, which is foundational to a

robust educational system and a thriving society. The significance of CPD is underscored by the assertion that no nation can rise above the quality of its educational system, and no educational system can rise above the quality of its teachers (Borg, 2019; Pishghadam et al., 2019). CPD helps teachers stay updated with the latest educational research, pedagogical techniques, and technological advancements. This ongoing development ensures that teachers can meet the evolving needs of their students and deliver education that is both relevant and impactful, thereby contributing to the overall quality of the educational system. One key aspect of CPD is its focus on education-based research practice. Teachers who engage in research-based practices are better equipped to understand and apply new teaching methodologies that are supported by empirical evidence. This aligns with Schön's (2019) theory of the reflective practitioner, which emphasizes the importance of reflective practice in professional development. By reflecting on their experiences and integrating new research findings into their teaching, educators can continually improve their instructional strategies. This reflective practice not only enhances their professional growth but also directly impacts student learning outcomes, leading to increased student engagement, understanding, and achievement. Moreover, CPD supports the development of teachers' pedagogical content knowledge (PCK), a concept introduced

by Shulman (2019). PCK is the blend of content and pedagogy that enables teachers to present subjects in ways that are comprehensible to students. Effective CPD programs help teachers develop deeper content knowledge and innovative pedagogical strategies, enabling them to make complex concepts accessible to diverse learners. By enhancing their PCK through continuous professional development, teachers can better address the varied learning needs of their students, providing more meaningful and effective learning experiences. Lastly, CPD fosters a culture of lifelong learning among teachers, which is crucial in today's fast-paced and ever-changing educational environment. According to Knowles' (2019) theory of andragogy, adult learners, including teachers, benefit from self-directed and experiential learning opportunities. CPD programs that incorporate these elements help teachers take ownership of their professional growth, encouraging them to pursue ongoing learning and development. This culture of lifelong learning not only benefits the teachers themselves but also sets a positive example for students, instilling in them the value of continuous improvement and adaptation. Consequently, by prioritizing CPD, educational systems can ensure that their teachers are well-prepared to face current and future challenges, ultimately leading to better educational outcomes for all students.

3.2.2. Collaboration and Support Networks—Teachers and principals often count on parents to help them create a positive learning environment in their schools. The family-school partnership can take the form of parents discussing education matters with their child, helping with homework, supervising their child's progress through education, communicating with school personnel, participating in decision making, and being involved in school activities

(LaRocque, Kleiman and Darling, 2011). Collaboration and support networks between families and schools are critical in creating a positive learning environment. Teachers and principals often rely on parents to foster this environment through active engagement and communication. The family-school partnership is rooted in the understanding that education extends beyond the classroom and is a shared responsibility. When parents discuss educational matters with

their children, help with homework, and supervise their educational progress, they reinforce the importance of learning and help establish consistent expectations and support. This active involvement can significantly influence a child's attitude towards education and their academic success (Epstein, 2021). Theories such as Epstein's Framework of Six Types of Involvement highlight the diverse ways in which parents can contribute to their children's education. These include parenting, communicating, volunteering, learning at home, decision making, and collaborating with the community. Each type emphasizes the multidimensional role parents play in their child's education, from supporting learning at home to participating in school activities and governance (Epstein, 2010). By engaging in these activities, parents help create a supportive and inclusive school culture that values and encourages student achievement. This holistic approach ensures that students receive a consistent message about the importance of education from both home and school, foster-

3.2.3. Seeking Student Feedback—Feedback is considered as a difficult issue in higher education arena. Although it is acknowledged as an essential element of improving the learning process of the students. Seeking student feedback is a critical yet complex issue in higher education. While feedback is universally recognized as a vital component of the learning process, ensuring it is effectively utilized remains challenging. According to Nicol and Macfarlane-Dick (2006), feedback helps students understand the quality of their work and the steps they need to take to improve. However, the effectiveness of feedback depends on how it is delivered and how students perceive and act on it. If feedback is not clear, constructive, and timely, it can lead to confusion and frustration, hindering rather than helping the learning process. One theoretical framework that sheds light

ing a more comprehensive and supportive learning environment. The involvement of parents in school activities and decision-making processes also aligns with Vygotsky's Social Development Theory, which posits that social interaction plays a fundamental role in the development of cognition. When parents actively participate in school functions and communicate with school personnel, they become integral parts of the educational community, enhancing the social learning environment for their children. This interaction not only supports the child's cognitive development but also strengthens the connection between the school and the community. By being involved in decision-making, parents can contribute valuable perspectives that help shape educational policies and practices, ensuring they are responsive to the needs of the student population (Vygotsky, 1978). This collaborative approach ultimately leads to a more dynamic and supportive educational environment where students can thrive.

on the complexities of feedback is the Cognitive Load Theory, which suggests that the amount and type of feedback provided can impact a student's ability to process and use the information effectively (Sweller, 1988). When feedback is overly detailed or delivered in a manner that overwhelms the student, it can exceed their cognitive capacity, making it difficult for them to focus on the key points that need improvement. Therefore, feedback should be designed to reduce cognitive load by being concise, focused on specific areas of improvement, and aligned with the student's current level of understanding and ability. Another important aspect to consider is the role of formative assessment and its relationship with feedback. Black and Wiliam (2020) argue that formative assessment, which involves providing ongoing feedback to students throughout the learning process, can

Fig. 4. Coping Mechanism in the challenges encountered in the Implementation of the Student-Centered Pedagogy

significantly enhance learning outcomes. This type of feedback allows students to make incremental improvements and adjust their learning strategies in real-time. However, for formative feedback to be effective, students need to be actively involved in the process. This involvement can be encouraged by creating a feedback culture where students feel comfortable seeking clarification and discussing feedback with their peers and instructors. Finally, the importance of fostering a feedback-rich environment cannot be overstated. Vygotsky’s (1978) Social Development Theory highlights the significance of social interaction in cognitive development. In a feedback-rich environment, students can en-

gage in meaningful dialogues with their instructors and peers, helping them to internalize feedback and apply it more effectively. Encouraging peer feedback and collaborative learning activities can also enhance the feedback process by providing multiple perspectives and promoting deeper understanding. Figure 4 outlines three primary coping mechanisms for addressing challenges encountered in implementing student-centered pedagogy: Continuous Professional Development (CPD), Collaboration and Support Networks, and Seeking Student Feedback. CPD is essential for teachers to stay updated with the latest educational research, teaching strategies, and technological advancements.

3.3. *Insights Drawn from the Findings of the Study*—Facilitative educators promote collaboration and peer-to-peer learning within the classroom. By facilitating discussions, group activities, and cooperative projects, they create op-

portunities for students to learn from each other and share diverse perspectives. This collaborative approach not only enriches the learning experience but also fosters a sense of community and mutual respect among students.

3.3.1. *Perceived as facilitators rather than authoritative figures*—

This means that they take on a supportive role, guiding students through their learning journey rather than simply imparting knowledge. The focus is on active learning and student engagement, where students are encouraged to take ownership of their learning and actively participate in classroom activities. In modern educational settings, teachers are increasingly perceived as facilitators rather than authoritative figures. This shift in perception reflects a broader pedagogical trend that emphasizes the role of educators as guides who support and mentor students through their learning journeys. Unlike traditional models where teachers were the primary source of knowledge, this facilitative approach encourages students to become active participants in their education. By fostering a supportive and collaborative classroom environment, teachers help students develop critical thinking skills and foster a sense of independence and responsibility in their learning processes (Brooks Brooks, 2023). The facilitator model aligns with constructivist theories of education, such as those proposed by Jean Piaget and Lev Vygotsky. Constructivism posits that learners construct their own understanding and knowledge of the world through experiences and reflecting on those experiences. Piaget's theory of cognitive development emphasizes that students learn best when they are actively involved in the learning process, exploring concepts, and solving problems on their own or in collaborative groups (Piaget, 1970). Vygotsky's concept of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) further supports this approach, suggesting that students learn most effectively when they receive guidance and sup-

port from a more knowledgeable other, often a teacher, within their ZPD (Vygotsky, 1978). This scaffolding process allows students to accomplish tasks they could not achieve independently, thereby enhancing their learning potential. Active learning is a key component of the facilitator approach, involving strategies that promote student engagement and participation in the learning process. Research has shown that active learning techniques, such as group discussions, problem-solving activities, and hands-on projects, lead to improved student outcomes compared to traditional lecture-based instruction (Prince, 2024). By engaging students in active learning, teachers as facilitators create opportunities for deeper understanding and retention of material. This method not only enhances cognitive development but also promotes social and emotional growth by encouraging collaboration and communication among students. Encouraging students to take ownership of their learning is another critical aspect of the facilitator role. When students are given the autonomy to set goals, make decisions, and reflect on their progress, they develop a stronger sense of agency and motivation. This empowerment is supported by self-determination theory, which emphasizes the importance of autonomy, competence, and relatedness in fostering intrinsic motivation (Deci Ryan, 2020). By creating a classroom environment that values student input and encourages self-directed learning, teachers can help students build the skills and confidence necessary to become lifelong learners. This approach not only prepares students for academic success but also equips them with the tools to navigate and thrive in an ever-changing world.

3.3.2. *Prioritize individual needs and interests*—This allows for personalized learning experiences, where students can explore topics and areas of interest that are relevant to them. Teachers strive to create a learning envi-

ronment that caters to the unique strengths and challenges of each student, fostering a sense of ownership and motivation in their learning. Prioritizing individual needs and interests in education allows for personalized learning ex-

periences, enabling students to engage deeply with topics that resonate with them. This approach recognizes that each student is unique, with distinct strengths, challenges, and areas of interest. By tailoring instruction to meet these individual needs, teachers can enhance student engagement and motivation, making learning more meaningful and relevant. Personalized learning not only helps students connect with the material on a deeper level but also encourages them to take ownership of their educational journey, fostering a lifelong love for learning. Creating a learning environment that caters to the unique strengths and challenges of each student is central to this personalized approach. Differentiated instruction, as advocated by Carol Ann Tomlinson (2001), is a key strategy in achieving this goal. Differentiated instruction involves providing different students with different avenues to learning, often in the same classroom. This might mean varying the content, process, products, or learning environment to address the diverse needs of students. By doing so, teachers can ensure that all students have access to learning that is challenging, engaging, and appropriate to their individual readiness levels, interests, and learning profiles. Personalized learning experiences also align with the principles of Universal Design for Learning (UDL), which promotes flexible learning environments that can accommodate

individual learning differences (Meyer, Rose, Gordon, 2021). UDL encourages teachers to provide multiple means of representation, engagement, and expression to support the diverse ways students learn. By incorporating UDL principles, teachers can create inclusive classrooms that not only address individual needs but also empower students to become active participants in their learning. This empowerment is crucial for developing self-regulation skills and a sense of agency, as students learn to set personal goals and monitor their progress toward achieving them. Moreover, focusing on individual needs and interests can significantly boost student motivation and academic achievement. When students see that their interests are valued and that they can pursue topics they are passionate about, they are more likely to be engaged and invested in their learning. This intrinsic motivation is critical for deep learning and academic success. Research by Deci and Ryan (2020) on self-determination theory highlights the importance of autonomy, competence, and relatedness in fostering intrinsic motivation. By prioritizing individual needs and interests, teachers can create a supportive learning environment that satisfies these fundamental psychological needs, leading to greater student motivation, higher academic performance, and more positive educational experiences overall.

3.3.3. Collaboration and Teamwork— Teachers in student-centered pedagogies promote collaboration and teamwork among students. They create opportunities for students to work together, encouraging them to share ideas, solve problems, and learn from each other. This collaborative approach not only enhances the learning experience but also fosters a sense of community in the classroom. Teachers in student-centered pedagogies also emphasize the development of critical thinking skills and

problem-solving abilities. They encourage students to think critically, analyze information, and make informed decisions. By promoting these skills, teachers aim to empower students to become independent learners who can navigate and succeed in a rapidly changing world. Collaboration and teamwork are fundamental components of student-centered pedagogies, where the role of the teacher shifts from the sole provider of knowledge to a facilitator of learning experiences. By promoting collabo-

ration, teachers create an environment where students actively engage with one another, sharing ideas and perspectives. This interaction is essential for deepening understanding and fostering critical thinking skills. According to Vygotsky's Social Development Theory, social interaction plays a crucial role in cognitive development, and learning is significantly enhanced when students work together within their Zone of Proximal Development (Vygotsky, 1978). Through collaborative activities, students are exposed to diverse viewpoints and strategies, enriching their learning process and enabling them to construct knowledge collectively. Creating opportunities for students to work together not only improves academic outcomes but also builds essential life skills. Collaborative learning environments encourage students to develop communication, problem-solving, and teamwork skills, which are critical for their future personal and professional lives. Johnson and Johnson's Cooperative Learning Theory underscores the importance of positive interdependence and individual accountability in group work. When students perceive that they can achieve their goals only if their group members also achieve theirs, they are more likely to contribute actively and support each other's learning (Johnson Johnson, 1989). This cooperative dynamic leads to a more engaged and motivated classroom, where students feel a sense of responsibility for their peers' success as well as their own. Furthermore, promoting collaboration and teamwork fosters a sense of community in the classroom, which is vital for creating a supportive and inclusive learning environment. When students collaborate, they build relationships and develop a sense of belonging, which enhances their overall well-being and academic performance. This sense of

community is particularly important for fostering a positive classroom climate where students feel safe to express their ideas and take intellectual risks. Research has shown that a strong sense of classroom community is associated with higher levels of student engagement, satisfaction, and achievement (Osterman, 2020). Figure 5 illustrates key educational management insights derived from a study focusing on three main components: teachers acting as facilitators rather than authoritative figures, the promotion of collaboration and teamwork, and the prioritization of individual needs. These insights emphasize a shift in educational approaches that cater to modern pedagogical standards. When teachers are perceived as facilitators, they support and guide students through their learning journeys instead of merely imparting knowledge. This approach fosters a more interactive and engaging learning environment where students are encouraged to take an active role in their education, enhancing their motivation and ownership of the learning process. Additionally, the diagram highlights the importance of collaboration and teamwork, which are crucial for creating a sense of community and enhancing the overall learning experience. By working together, students can share ideas, solve problems collectively, and learn from one another, which not only deepens their understanding of the subject matter but also develops essential interpersonal skills. Prioritizing individual needs ensures that each student's unique strengths and challenges are addressed, providing personalized learning experiences that can boost their academic success and personal growth. Together, these components form a comprehensive approach to educational management that aims to create a more inclusive, supportive, and effective learning environment.

Fig. 5. Generated Themes on the Educational management insights gained from the findings of the study

4. Implications and Future Directions

A brief overview of the study was presented in this chapter. It was followed by implications based on the findings of this study. This study aimed to uncover the experiences of teachers in the implementation of student-centered pedagogies in the classroom. This paper utilized a phenomenological study, participated in by purposively sampled teachers who best met the purpose of the study. Data gathered were analyzed through thematic analysis.

4.1. Findings—In the first objective. The first theme that emerged was support student learning experiences. These were the most well-considered and motivated active learning methods out of all of them. They were referred to as affective strategies when learners demonstrate positive affective reactions during the listening process. According to research, people who were driven and excited to listen were more engaged during the process, whereas others who were hesitant or felt under pressure to listen became passive—in other words, less successful learners. The second theme that emerged was active listening to student’s needs. In primary education, a listening culture that renders kids docile has endured for years. This

culture’s predilection for pupils to sit still, listen to the teacher silently, and not make noise in class has hindered students’ ability to self-actualize and acquire language abilities like listening. However, listening was a multifaceted activity in which people engaged with thoughts, feelings, and spoken and nonverbal expressions. Learners should employ language skills in formal learning situations and be free to actualize their language skills without feeling pressurized, just as they do in their social lives. The final theme that emerged was Adaptable Professional. This means that teachers could continue to develop their adaptability skills by seeking professional development opportunities, attending workshops, and collaborating with colleagues.

Staying updated with current research and best practices in education could provide new ideas and strategies to implement in the classroom. Reflecting on our teaching practices and seeking feedback from students and colleagues helps us grow as adaptable professionals. Adaptable teachers embrace a growth mindset, believing their teaching methods could evolve and improve. They viewed challenges as opportunities for learning and were open to trying new approaches that better meet the needs of their students. The second objective was to discover the coping practices of the teachers. The first theme that emerged was continuous professional development. It has been challenging to draw conclusions about the significance and attention paid to these aspects of enhancing teacher success through teachers' perspectives of research and CPD needs. The apparent flaws in the nation's teacher education and preparation programs, which prioritize increasing teachers' content knowledge growth at the expense of other equally crucial components of successful teaching, such as teachers' CPD needs and perspectives on and involvement in research. The second emerging theme was collaboration and network support. participating in school gives

4.2. Implications—The purpose of this study was to investigate and narrate teachers' experiences on the learner-centered pedagogies in the classroom. Based on the analysis conveyed it could be concluded that in a student-centered pedagogy in the classroom, teachers play a crucial role as facilitators. They prioritize individual needs and interests, ensuring that each student's unique learning style and preferences are taken into account. Teachers promote collaboration and teamwork among students, encouraging them to work together and learn from one another. The first concept developed for the first objective was supporting student learning experiences. These were the

parents the opportunity to learn about the educational system, gain firsthand knowledge of the learning environment, show their children the value of education, and shape their behavior by setting consistent norms. Previous research has indicated that parental involvement in a child's education improves student outcomes, though the impact was largely dependent on the level of involvement. Parental involvement in school activities has been favorably correlated with kid achievement, among other factors. The third emerging theme was seeking student feedback. Feedback was considered a difficult issue in the higher education arena. Although it was acknowledged as an essential element of improving the learning process of the students. Considering feedback and its value and effectiveness in student learning, a substantial and growing body of research in higher education environments could be found. Feedback was considered a vital approach to facilitate students' development as independent learners in order to monitor, evaluate, and regulate their own learning. The impact of feedback on future practice and the development of students' learning was highlighted by many researchers.

most well-considered and driven active learning approaches of them all. Affective techniques were used when learners exhibited positive affective reactions during the listening process. According to the study, those who were motivated and delighted to listen were more engaged during the process, whereas those who were hesitant or felt pressured to listen became passive, that was, less successful learners. The second theme that emerged was Active listening to students' needs. For years, a listening culture in primary education has kept children passive. The culture's preference for kids to sit still, listen to the teacher quietly, and make little disturbance in class has hampered students'

capacity to self-actualize and learn language skills such as listening. However, listening is a diverse action in which people interact with their thoughts, feelings, and spoken and non-verbal expressions. Learners should use language skills in formal learning circumstances and be free to practice them without feeling pressured, just as they do in their social lives. The final theme that evolved was "Adaptable Professional." This indicates that teachers could improve their adaptation abilities by seeking professional development opportunities, attending workshops, and working with colleagues. Staying up to date on current educational research and best practices could lead to fresh ideas and tactics to employ in the classroom. Reflecting on our teaching techniques and soliciting feedback from students and colleagues helps us develop as flexible professionals. Adaptable teachers have a growth mentality, thinking that their teaching techniques may change and improve. They sought obstacles as opportunities for learning and were willing to attempt new techniques that better fulfill the requirements of their students. The second objective was to learn about the teachers' coping strategies. The first theme that emerged was Continuous Professional De-

velopment. It has been difficult to draw conclusions about the significance and attention paid to these aspects in Iran's educational system due to a lack of studies on enhancing teacher success through teachers' perspectives on research and CPD needs. The obvious inadequacies in the nation's teacher education and preparation programs stress expanding teachers' topic knowledge growth over other equally important components of successful teaching, such as instructors' CPD needs, perspectives on and participation in research. The second rising theme was collaboration and network support. Participating in school allows parents to learn about the educational system, obtain firsthand knowledge of the learning environment, demonstrate the significance of education to their children, and impact their conduct by establishing consistent norms. The third emerging theme was requesting student feedback. Feedback was regarded as a difficult issue in the higher education sector. Although feedback was recognized as a crucial component of improving students' learning processes, there was a considerable and growing body of study in higher education environments on its usefulness and effectiveness.

4.3. Future Directions—The research study was limited by its qualitative nature and by the research methodology itself. Due to the variables concerned, objectivity is often an important issue because the researcher interprets the data based on her understanding of the descriptions, perceptions, and insights provided by teachers who implement Learner-Centered Pedagogies in the classroom. The research findings would likely contribute to the research literature and inform and inspire all other teachers in public and private schools. DepEd Officials. for education officials to come up with new programs related to improving student-centered classrooms. Teachers also

strive to create inclusive and equitable learning environments, where every student feels valued and respected. This approach encourages active learning, with students actively participating and engaging in the learning process. It also fosters personalized learning experiences, allowing students to pursue their interests and passions. Ultimately, the goal is to develop independent learners who are motivated and empowered to take ownership of their education. School Administrators. The data gathered may serve as research-based information that will be useful in motivating and providing technical assistance to teachers in innovating the methodologies applicable in the school context in information

communication technology, including its challenges and opportunities. Teachers. for them to improve the teaching-learning process in distant learning settings, consequently increasing academic performance through the implementation of new student-centered classrooms. In a student-centered pedagogy, teachers are seen as facilitators who guide and support students in their learning journey. They prioritized individual needs and interests, recognizing that each student was unique and had different learning styles and preferences. Teachers promote collaboration and teamwork, encouraging students to work together and learn from one another. They emphasize critical thinking and problem-solving skills, providing opportunities for students to analyze and evaluate information, think critically, and come up with creative solutions. Stakeholders. The community was the best recipient of new normal innovations in the institution. Data gathered from this research may serve as a good basis for stakeholders to help improve the school's organizational changes. Teachers prioritize individual needs and interests, recognizing that each student has unique strengths and weaknesses. By promoting collaboration and teamwork, teachers encourage students to work together and learn from one another. This collaborative environment fosters a sense of community and helps students develop important social skills. Future Researchers. The results generated from this research may provide comprehensive data for conducting future research with similar or relevant scope. This is additional empirical data for an efficient learning process. Furthermore, a student-centered pedagogy emphasizes critical thinking and problem-solving skills. They may encourage students to think critically, analyze information, and develop their own opinions. This approach helps students develop a deeper understanding of the subject matter and prepares them for real-world challenges. Creating inclusive and equitable learning environments is another essential aspect of a student-centered pedagogy. Teachers strive to create an atmosphere where every student feels valued and respected. They acknowledge and celebrate diversity, ensuring that all students have equal opportunities to learn and succeed. Overall, a student-centered pedagogy encourages active learning and student engagement. Teachers aim to create personalized learning experiences that cater to individual student needs and interests. This approach helps students take ownership of their learning and become independent learners.

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